

Table 1

P value (r^2)	Asymptote	I_{50}	Peak slope
group	0.42 (0.02)	0.32 (0.14)	0.59 (0.05)
muscle	< 0.0001 (0.21)	< 0.0001 (0.66)	< 0.05 (0.08)
response	< 0.001 (0.17)	< 0.0001 (0.66)	0.11 (0.09)
group x response	< 0.05 (0.19)*	= 0.81 (0.69)	= 0.96 (0.10)
group x muscle x response	0.86 (0.19)	0.06 (0.69)	0.31 (0.10)

*Post hoc Student t test to compare marginal means Controls vs. ALS: H-reflex $p = 0.58$ and M response $p = 0.06$

Table 2

P value (r^2)	Ratio H/M	
	Asymptote	Peak slope
group	< 0.001 (0.01)	< 0.05 (0)
group x muscle	0.87 (0.01)	0.64 (0)

Link with clinical features:

Asymptote ratio increased in spastic patients ($p < 0.001$), in hyperreflexic ($p < 0.05$) and off-riluzole ($p < 0.05$)

Peak slope ratio increased off-riluzole ($p < 0.05$)

Table 3

P values (f^2)	Asymptotes	I_{50}	Peak slope
group	0.052 (0.36)	0.18 (0.09)	0.20 (0.09)
Response	< 0.001 (0.36)	< 0.001 (0.09)**	0.27 (0.09)
group x response	< 0.001 (0.36)*	0.058 (0.09)	0.06 (0.09)

* *Post hoc* Student t test to compare marginal means Controls vs. ALS: H-reflex $p = 0.27$ and MEP $p < 0.001$

** *Post hoc* Student t test to compare marginal means Controls vs. ALS: H-reflex $p = 0.7865$ and MEP $p < 0.05$

Absence of monosynaptic excitation in a deafferented patient except in hand muscle

After two episodes of extensive sensory polyneuropathy, the patient exhibited a complete loss of touch, vibration, pressure, and kinaesthetic senses, along with the absence of tendon reflexes in all four limbs (deafferented patient GL). In collaboration with Prs. E. Pierrot-Deseilligny, H. Hultborn, and J.B. Nielsen, V. Marchand-Pauvert conducted a series of electrophysiological experiments in this patient 20 years ago (unpublished data). The present data originates from EMG in abductor digiti minimi (ADM), flexor carpi radialis (FCR), extensor carpi radialis (ECR), soleus and quadriceps recorded during isolated, tonic, voluntary contractions at 20% of the maximum force. Electrical stimuli (1-ms pulse duration, 1-Hz frequency, 1.5 x MT) were applied to the ulnar nerve at wrist level (ADM), the median nerve at elbow level (FCR), the radial nerve at arm level (ECR), and the tibial nerve for soleus and quadriceps (heteronymous monosynaptic excitation; *Meunier S. et al. Exp Brain Res. 1993;96(3):534-44*). In 2004 (upper limb), a Labview-NI program was used to record EMG over predefined windows, which randomly alternated recording with and without stimulation (control in black vs. conditioned EMG in red). In 2007 (lower limb), a Notocord-hem program was used to record EMG continuously (compare pre- vs. post-stimulus EMG). Any early facilitation corresponding to group Ia monosynaptic excitation was not observed in all muscles except ADM. Considering the afferent and efferent conduction times (estimated with the distance between the stimulation site and the C6 root, and the conduction velocity in group Ia fibers and motor axons), a monosynaptic excitation could be expected at around 20 ms in ADM. An early facilitation was consistently observed in ADM that aligned with the latency of a monosynaptic group Ia excitation. This facilitation occurred at the threshold intensity for M response and above (it was also observed at rest; data not recorded). Since this response couldn't be an H-reflex, it was likely the result of motor axon activation mediating F-wave.